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Research Article

MEDICAL STUDENTS' PERCEPTION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF OBJECTIVE STRUCTURED CLINICAL EXAMINATION (OSCE) IN PHASE TWO (THE PRE-CLINICAL PHASE) AT KING SAUD BIN ABDULAZIZ UNIVERSITY FOR HEALTH SCIENCES

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Abstract:

Background: Objective structures clinical examination (OSCE) is one of the most common methods used to test aspects of clinical competency in healthcare education. Nowadays most of the medical schools practice OSCEs but the implementation phase differs, some medical schools use OSCEs exclusively in their clinical phases and some use it early in their pre-clinical phases.

Aim: To explore the perceptions of the phase three students about the effectiveness of (OSCE) in the pre-clinical phase at King Saud bin Abdulaziz University for Health Sciences.

Methods and Material: Cross-sectional study was done on 193 students by distributing Validated questionnaires 2 on all male and female medical students who are in phase three in 2017/2018 year in KSAU-HS in Riyadh. Data was entered and analyzed using SPSS version 20. For categorical data such as gender, two-sample t test was used. For quantitative data such as age and GPA, correlation coefficient method was used.

Results: 193 students with mean age of 23.47 were included in the study. About 59% of the students agreed that OSCEs were a useful experience. However only 33.2% agreed that OSCE scores provide a true measure of essential clinical skills. Also, 46.6% of the students think that personality and social relation will affect OSCE scores. T test and correlation coefficient values showed that there was no significant difference between the demographic data in the study.

Conclusions: Students consider OSCEs as valuable and practical experiences in the pre-clinical phase but need improvement in the organization and the evaluation.

Key words: OSCE, healthcare-education, KSAUHS, Assessment, Medical-Students

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INTRODUCTION:

Clinical competence has been under discussion for a long time in how can be defined and assessed. There are a lot of definitions for clinical competence. One of the common research that addressed clinical competence articles define it as the habitual and judicious use of communication, knowledge, technical skills, clinical reasoning, emotions, values, and reflection in daily practice for the benefit of the individual and the community being served.[1] It is important to judge the competency of health professionals early, because each clinical skill may need a long time to develop.[2] This is significant in order to decide if the students and the trainees can pass their course or proceed to higher levels. Inaccuracy in such judgments may put patients at risk. [3]

Objective structures clinical examination (OSCE) is one of the most common methods used to test aspects of clinical competency in healthcare education. [4] There are many features of a suitable and valuable test. Van der Vleuten explained five important criteria to judge an assessment test namely: reliability, validity, educational impact, cost efficiency and acceptability of the test. [5] OSCEs were developed to replace the traditional form of clinical assessment, which lacks some of the criteria that were mentioned.[5] OSCEs can have an influence on the medical students in a positive way. It improves their performance, confidence and communication skills. [6] In contrast, OSCEs may have some disadvantages. It can be a stressful test to be carried out by some students. Also, the students mainly focus on the checklist, which may affect other aspects of the clinical competence for some medical students. [3]

OSCEs cost the medical schools a lot of effort and money, such as, availability of suitable rooms, expert examiners, proctors and medical supplies. In addition, OSCEs stations are required to be improved and updated regularly. [7] Nowadays most of the medical schools practice OSCEs but the implementation phase differs, some medical schools use OSCEs exclusively in their clinical phases and some use it early in their pre-clinical phases. King Saud bin Abdulaziz University for Health Sciences adopts a problem-based learning curriculum, which exposes the students to the clinical field early. [8] Moreover, its medical college is one of the few medical colleges in Saudi Arabia which practices OSCEs early, from the pre-clinical phase. [9]

Medical education is moving towards student's centered education, so student's perception is one of the most valid methods to assess any academic activity. [6] Many studies have been done to explore students' perception on OSCEs in different fields. A study done in Nigeria, in which about 60% of the sample agreed that the OSCE precisely measured their comprehension and ability, and 55% stated that OSCE improved their skill in communication. [6] Another study was done on third-year nursing students in Saudi Arabia about OSCE as a new clinical assessment method. 87% of the students agreed that task performance during OSCE was educational and interesting; the majority of the students (89%) preferred OSCE over other forms of assessments. However, 78% perceived OSCE to be a stressful experience. [10] On other hand, a recent research was conducted on 246 senior medical students in Saudi Arabia had a different result. 52% of them denied that OSCE provided opportunity to learn real life scenarios and 77% of students agreed that Passing or failing the OSCE was not a true measure of clinical skills. [11]

It is important for medical colleges to determine the educational impact of OSCEs on the clinical competence of the pre-clinical phase students and whether if OSCEs are needed in this phase or not. This study aimed at exploring the perceptions of the students about the effectiveness of objective structured clinical examination (OSCE) in the pre-clinical phase at King Saud bin Abdulaziz University for Health Sciences.

METHODOLOGY:

Study Area/Setting:

King Saud Bin Abdulaziz University for Health Sciences has three campuses located in King Abdulaziz Medical Cities and is under the supervision of the Saudi National Guard Health Affairs. KSAU-HS was established on 25 March 2005. The study was conducted at College of Medicine in Riyadh campus in both male and female buildings.

Study Subjects:

All male and female medical students who are in phase three in 2017/2018 year (batch 11 and batch 12) in KSAU-HS in Riyadh. There are 170 male students in their fifth year and there are 118 male students in their sixth year. There are 60 female students in their fifth year and there are 40 female students in their sixth year.

Study Design:

Cross-sectional study survey using validated questionnaire with various domains, The questionnaire developed by Pierre et al (2004) [2] and was modified for the purpose of this study.

Sample Size:

Previous study showed that prevalence of 60% agreed that the OSCE accurately measured their knowledge and skill and enhanced their communication skill. The total number of the subjects in the study was 193 students, with confidence level of 95%, the expected margin of error was 6.91%.

Data Collection methods, instruments used, measurements:

Data was collected by distributing the questionnaire papers to the students in the classes. The students were asked to put the questionnaires in a box after they finish. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire developed by Pierre et al (2004) [2] and was modified for the purpose of this study.

The internal consistency of the questionnaire calculated by using Cronbach's alpha coefficient was equal to 0.766 for the whole questionnaire and for the factors were between (0.519, and 0.899). The questionnaire was in English.

The variables include the demographic section and the perception of the students to evaluate the structure and organization of the OSCE, the validity and reliability of the OSCE, and rate the OSCE in relation to other evaluation tools. A five-point Likert / type scale that indicates degree of agreement was used to assess most of the dimensions in the questionnaire and a three-point scale was used for rating OSCE in relation to other assessment methods.

The quantitative and qualitative data were included. The quantitative data were the age and GPA while the qualitative were the gender and the batch year.

DATA MANAGEMENT AND ANALYSIS PLAN:

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 20. The Categorical data such as the gender and the batch year was described by frequencies and percentages while the numerical data such as the age and GPA by mean and standard deviation.

The perception of the students toward OSCEs was compared with those of the demographic data by the appropriate tests. For categorical data such as gender two sample t test (student -t test) was used. For quantitative data such as age and GPA, correlation coefficient method was used. A test with a P value of less than 0.05 statistically considered as significant.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:

The confidentiality of participants (the students) was protected by two ways. First, the names and the ID numbers were not collected from the subjects. Second, we asked the students to put the questionnaire papers in a box. A consent form designed by King Abdullah International Medical Research Center was attached with the questionnaire.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the total sample size (n=193) is 23.47 with standard deviation of 2.272 and minimum of 21 and maximum of 32. The majority of the sample size were males by 72.5 %, where 27.5 % for females. The mean GPA is 3.93 of 5.0 with SD 0.523 and Min of 3.4, Max of 4.91. Regarding the academic year level distribution, 86 students (44.6%) from the fifth year while 107 students (55.4%) from the sixth year (table 1).

Table1: Descriptive Statistics for Subject demographics N= 193.

Characteristics		
Sex	Male	N=140 (72.5%)
	Female	N=53 (27.5%)
Age		Mean= 23.47
GPA		Mean= 3.93
Academic year	5th year	N=86 (44.6%)
	6th year	N=107 (55.4)
Stream	One	N=163 (84.5%)
	Two	N=30 (15.5%)

The medical college of King Saud Bin Abdulaziz University for Health Sciences has two types of students, students who entered the college after the high school called stream one students and the students who entered the college after having the bachelor's degree called stream two. In the study, stream one students are the highest percentage by 84.5% where the stream two is 15.5%.

A five-point Likert type scale that indicates degree of agreement was used to assess most of the dimensions in the questionnaire and a three-point scale was used for rating OSCE in relation to other assessment methods. In the results, strongly agree scale was added to agree scale and considered both as an agreement and also the same was for strongly disagree scale and the disagree scale, so the results were explain as an agreement, disagreement and neutral.

Regarding the perception of the students to evaluate the structure and organization of the OSCE, 37% of

the students agreed that OSCE exams were well structured and sequenced while 24% disagreed and 39% are Neutral. 38% of the students agreed that the exams were well administered while 16,5% disagreed and 45.5% are neutral. 42% of the students agreed that the instructions were clear and unambiguous while 29,5 disagreed and 28.5% are neutral.

Regarding the perception of the students to evaluate the OSCE attributes, 49% of the students agreed that wide knowledge area was covered while 16.5% disagreed and 34.5% are neutral. 48% of the students agreed that wide range of clinical skills was covered while 22% disagreed and 30% are neutral. However, only 28% agreed that they were aware of the level of information needed for OSCE stations while 45% disagreed and 27% are neutral. Also, 51% of students agreed that they needed more time at stations while 23% disagreed and 26% are neutral. On term of the exam stress, 65% agreed that the OSCE exams were very stressful and only 10% disagreed. (figure 1)

Figure 1: perception of the students to evaluate the OSCE attributes

Regarding the perception of the students to evaluate the quality of OSCE performance, 64% of the students agreed that they were fully aware of the nature of the exam while 13% disagreed and 23% are neutral. 40.5% of the students agreed that the tasks required in the OSCE exams were reflected those taught while 21% disagreed. Close to a third of the students (29.5%) agreed that they felt the setting and context at each station is authentic while 25.5% disagreed. 52% agreed that OSCE exams provided opportunities to learn while 20% disagree.

Regarding the perception of the students to evaluate the validity and reliability of the OSCE, 57% of the students agreed that OSCE exams were practical and useful experience while 15.5% disagreed and 27.5% are neutral. However, only 33% agreed that OSCE scores provided a true measure of essential clinical skills while 34% disagreed and 33% are neutral. Moreover, only 22% agreed that personality and social relations will not affect OSCE scores while 47% disagreed and 31% are neutral (figure 2).

Figure 2: perception of the students to evaluate the validity and reliability of the OSCE

Regarding the perception of the students to rate the OSCE in relation to other evaluation tools, 73.1% considered the difficulty of OSCE as a moderate while 7.3% as an easy exam and 19.7% as a difficult exam. When compare it with other exams, it was considered easier than MCQ exam and more difficult

than OSPE exam. Twenty eight percent of the students preferred to use OSCE more as an assessment tool and 8.3% preferred to use it less and 63.7% are neutral.

When compare it with other exams, OSCE exam was

preferred to be used more than MCQ exam and OSPE exam. Twenty two percent of the students preferred to use MCQ exam more as an assessment tool and 11.5% preferred to use it less and 66.5% are neutral. Twenty one percent of the students preferred to use OSPE exam more as an assessment tool and 13.5% preferred to use it less and 65.5% are neutral. T test and correlation coefficient values showed no significant difference between the factors in the study, like age, gender, GPA, academic year level and the stream type.

DISCUSSION:

The idea of doing this research was to know the perception of the students practicing OSCE in the pre-clinical phase in terms of the organization, OSCE attributes, the quality of OSCE performance, the validity and reliability of OSCE and comparing OSCE to other evaluation tools.

For the organization, at least third of the students (37%) agreed that OSCE exams were well structured and sequential while 24% disagreed and 39% are Neutral. The medical college of KSAUHS always making efforts to have the best organization as possible by continuous evaluation and taking feedbacks on every OSCE exam and try to improve it, but the problem was the limited facilities especially the evaluators with huge number of students in the pre-clinical phase. The OSCE protocol keeps the students in the waiting areas after dividing them into groups to enter the OSCE stations in an organized way. Although in the pre-clinical phase the number of the students in each block was more than that of the clinical phase, both phases usually have similar quantity of the facilities. Unfortunately, students in the pre-clinical phase had to wait for more than four hours, which made most of the students exhausted and stressed.

For the OSCE attributes, most of the students (49%) agreed that wide knowledge area was covered while 16.5% disagreed and 34.5% were neutral. On term of the exam stress, 65% agreed that the OSCE exams were very stressful and only 10% disagreed. This conclusion is similar to that found in a study was done on third-year nursing students in Saudi Arabia about OSCE as a new clinical assessment method, 78% perceived OSCE to be a stressful experience. [10]

For the quality of OSCE performance, about third of the students (29.5%) agreed that they felt the setting

and context at each station was authentic while 25.5 were against this end results. Recent research study was conducted on 246 senior medical students in Saudi Arabia showed different results .52% of them denied that OSCE provided opportunity to learn real life scenarios. [11]

For the validity and reliability of OSCE, 57% of the students agreed that OSCE exams were practical and introduced useful experience while 15.5% disagreed and 27.5 were neutral, which was less than a study was done on nursing students in Saudi Arabia, which showed 87% of the students agreed that the task performance during OSCE was educational and interesting. [10]

In our study, only 33% agreed that OSCE scores provided a true measure of essential clinical skills while 34% disagreed and 33% were neutral, Moreover, there was a diversity between the similar studies illustrated in the literatures. For example, a study was done in Nigeria, about 60% of the sample agreed that the OSCE precisely measured their comprehension and ability. Another research was conducted in Saudi Arabia showed different results, 77% of students agreed that Passing or failing the OSCE was not a true measure of clinical skills. [11]

Forty-six and six tenths percent of the students in our study thought that personality and social relation affect OSCE scores. This conclusion could be attributed to two factors. First, usually the students in the same OSCE exam will not have the same evaluators as they are divided into groups. Second, the evaluators know some of the students before the OSCE exam.

Regarding the perception of the students to rate OSCE in relation to other evaluation tools, 28% of the students preferred to use OSCE more as an assessment tool, while, 8.3% were less acceptable and 63.7 were neutral. Comparing OSCE other exams, it was preferred to be used more than MCQ exam and OSPE exam.

Students suggest and confirm that OSCEs are valuable and give practical experiences in the pre-clinical phase but need more improvement in the organization and evaluation methodology. The students need well-defined instructions in term of the level of the information needed for every OSCE exam. The coordinator should improve OSCE station especially the checklist to provide a true measure of essential clinical skill as much as possible. To decrease personality and social relation effectiveness on OSCE scores, the evaluator can evaluate the

student by Video from a different room without knowing the names of the students (Blind methods).

In a study done in Saudi Arabia, the majority of the students (89%) preferred OSCE over other forms of assessments. [10]

CONCLUSION:

Students suggest and confirm that OSCEs are valuable and give practical experiences in the pre-clinical phase but need more improvement in the organization and evaluation methodology. The students need well-defined instructions in term of the level of the information needed for every OSCE exam. The coordinator should improve OSCE station especially the checklist to provide a true measure of essential clinical skill as much as possible. To decrease personality and social relation effectiveness on OSCE scores, the evaluator can evaluate the student by Video from a different room without knowing the names of the students (Blind methods). In conclusion, we recommend practicing OSCE exams in the pre-clinical phase if the college has suitable facilities and resources to conduct the exams.

REFERENCES:

1. Epstein R, Hundert E. Defining and Assessing Professional Competence. *JAMA*. 2002; 287:226.
2. Pierre R, Wierenga A, Barton M, Branday J, Christie C. Student evaluation of an OSCE in paediatrics at the University of the West Indies, Jamaica. *BMC Med Educ*. 2004;4(22).
3. Gormley G. Summative OSCEs in undergraduate medical education. *Ulster Med J*. 2011; 8:127-132.
4. Newble D. Techniques for measuring clinical competence: objective structured clinical examinations. *Med Educ*. 2004; 38:199-203.
5. Van Der Vleuten C. The assessment of professional competence: Developments, research and practical implications. *Adv Health Sci Educ Theory Pract*. 1996; 1:41-67.
6. Nasir A, Yusuf A, Abdur-Rahman L, Babalola O, Adeyeye A, Popoola A, Adeniran J. Medical Students' Perception of Objective Structured Clinical Examination: A Feedback for Process Improvement. *J Surg Educ*. 2014; 71:701-706.
7. Sudan R, Clark P, Henry B. Cost and logistics for implementing the American College of Surgeons objective structured clinical examination. *Am J Surg*. 2015; 209:140-144.
8. Harden R, Lilley P, Patrício M. The definitive guide to the OSCE 1st ed. Edinburgh: Elsevier; 2016;224-228.
9. Alaidarous S, Mohamed T, Masuadi E, Wali S, AlMalki A. Saudi Internal Medicine Residents' Perceptions of the Objective Structured Clinical Examination as a Formative Assessment Tool. *Health Prof Educ*. 2016; 2:121-129.
10. Hatamleh W, Abu Sabeeb Z. Nursing Students Perceptions of an Objectives Structured Clinical Examination. *Int J Healthc Sci*. 2015; 2:52-56.
11. Alghamdi K, Katib B, Alhoqail A, Al-khatib T. Perception and acceptance of senior medical students at King Abdulaziz University of the use of Objective Structured Clinical Examination as a tool of assessment. *MedEdPublish*. 2016;5.